

Transformational Leadership and Organizational Behavior: The Mediating Role of Commitment to Change among Teachers in Davao City

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Abstract

This study assessed the mediating effect of commitment to change on the relationship between transformational leadership and the organizational behavior of teachers in Davao City. The research design employed in this study is a quantitative, non-experimental, correlational research design with adopted instruments from Fedor, Caldwell, & Herold (2006) Commitment to Change Scale, Avolio & Bass (2004) Transformational Leadership Scale, and Bateman & Crant (1993) Organizational Behavior Scale. The researchers selected 183 teachers as respondents through proportional quota sampling. The researchers used mean, Pearson-product moment correlation, and Path Analysis to analyze the data. The findings revealed that the levels of transformational leadership, organizational behavior, and commitment to change are evident among teachers in Davao City. Moreover, the researchers found that there is a significant relationship between transformational leadership and commitment to change (p -value=.001), commitment to change and organizational behavior (p -value=.000), and transformational leadership and organizational behavior (p -value=.004). Furthermore, the results showed a partial mediation of commitment to change in the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational behavior. With these findings, the researchers recommend that further investigation should be undertaken to understand the dynamics between commitment to change, transformational leadership, and organizational behavior among teachers. Also, the researchers recommend exploring the leadership styles, practices, and challenges faced by school heads in promoting a culture of change within educational institutions and examining the specific leadership styles employed by the school head that could potentially impact the teachers' commitment to change and organizational behavior.

Keywords: *Transformational Leadership, Organizational Behavior, Commitment to Change, Teachers, Davao City.*

Suggested citation: De Los Santos, J.B., Ignalig, W.O., & Cayogyog, A.O. (2024). Transformational Leadership and Organizational Behavior: The Mediating Role of Commitment to Change among Teachers in Davao City. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(3), 161-171. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2024.1(3).14

Introduction

The rise of more collaborative, adaptable types of leadership is posing a challenge to traditional models of leadership, which are frequently characterized by hierarchical structures and top-down decision-making (Yukl, 2014). A careful examination of how leadership relates to elements including employee demographics, company culture, and external environmental factors is necessary due to its dynamic

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nature (Avolio et al., 2020). Moreover, this investigation is made more complex by the dynamic nature of organizational behavior, which is impacted by a variety of elements such as group dynamics and individual psychology (Judge & Piccolo, 2019). Alqatawenhi (2018) asserted that change occurs everywhere at an increasingly complex rate so leadership and change might have become one of the big challenges facing modern organizations. The ability to deal with change effectively requires leadership behavior to coincide with the work of the organization which is called transformational leadership.

In the dynamic landscape of organizational management in the United States, the intersection of organizational leadership and behavior presents a compelling area of research fraught with challenges and opportunities. Despite the nation's long-standing tradition of pioneering management theories and practices, contemporary organizations grapple with multifaceted issues concerning leadership effectiveness and organizational behavior adaptation (Dávila et al., 2019). One prominent challenge lies in the realm of leadership diversity and inclusion. Despite strides toward inclusivity, disparities persist in leadership representation across gender, ethnicity, and other demographic dimensions, posing significant barriers to fostering a truly inclusive organizational culture (Chin et al., 2021). Moreover, the rapidly evolving nature of work, accelerated by technological advancements and globalization, necessitates a reevaluation of traditional leadership paradigms to effectively navigate complexities such as remote work arrangements, digital transformation, and cross-cultural collaboration (Bass & Riggio, 2020). Additionally, the intricate dynamics of organizational behavior, encompassing aspects such as employee engagement, motivation, and team dynamics, underscore the need for comprehensive research to unravel the underlying mechanisms driving individual and collective behavior within American organizations (LePine et al., 2016).

The study of organizational leadership and behavior is becoming more and more important, with unique opportunities and problems in Luzon, Philippines. Organizations in Luzon face complex challenges related to organizational dynamics and leadership efficacy despite the region's tremendous industrial boom and rapid economic expansion (Garcia et al., 2018). The areas of succession planning and leadership development are two major issues. Effective leadership that can navigate difficult issues like talent retention, digital transformation, and global competition is becoming more and more important as firms work to adapt to evolving market demands and technology improvements (Dumlao et al., 2020). However, the lack of strategic succession planning activities and limited access to programs for leadership development prevent the establishment of a strong leadership pipeline, which in turn hinders organizational agility and resilience. Furthermore, the study of organizational behavior is made more challenging by the distinct sociocultural environment of Luzon. Organizations face difficulties in developing harmonious team dynamics, encouraging employee engagement, and reducing intergroup conflicts when dealing with a varied workforce that is marked by differing cultural norms, values, and communication styles (Bautista et al., 2019). Furthermore, the area of diversity and inclusivity in leadership presents a significant challenge. Organizations need to establish inclusive leadership strategies that cross cultural barriers to culture and provide fair chances for all workers because Mindanao is home to a varied range of ethnic groups, religions, and languages (Ramos et al., 2020). However, attempts to develop a truly inclusive workplace culture are frequently hampered by ingrained cultural norms and historical legacies of prejudice, which contribute to inequality and impair organizational performance.

The importance of leadership and behavior in organizations transcends its boundaries and has wider cultural and economic implications. In addition to improving an organization's reputation and stakeholder trust, cultivating a culture of ethical leadership and employee involvement promotes long-term sustainability and social responsibility (Treviño et al., 2014). Furthermore, knowing the sociological and psychological foundations of organizational behavior makes it easier to create evidence-based interventions for problems like employee well-being, diversity management, and workplace stress (Greenberg & Baron, 2017). Taking these factors into account, research on organizational leadership and behavior is still very relevant and crucial for tackling today's issues and promoting organizational excellence in the twenty-first century. Scholars and practitioners can jointly advance knowledge and develop strategies to improve leadership effectiveness, foster a positive organizational culture, and

promote sustainable organizational outcomes in a constantly changing landscape by utilizing theoretical frameworks, empirical research methods, and practical insights.

By focusing on this specific context, the study aims to provide insights that are not only theoretically relevant but also practically applicable, offering recommendations for educational leaders, policymakers, and practitioners to enhance the quality of education in the region. Through an in-depth examination of the interplay between transformational leadership, organizational behavior, and commitment to change, this study aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge in educational leadership and management, to foster a positive and adaptive educational environment for both teachers and students in Davao City.

This study aims to determine the mediating effect of commitment to change on the relationship between transformational leadership and the organizational behavior of teachers in Davao City. Specifically, this study aims to answer the following: (1) What is the level of transformational leadership of teachers in Davao City in terms of idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, individual consideration, and inspirational motivation?; (2) What is the level of organizational behavior of teachers in Davao City?; (3) What is the level of commitment to change of teachers in Davao City in terms of affective, continuance, and normative?; (4) Is there a significant relationship between transformational leadership and the organizational behavior of teachers in Davao City?; (5)? Is there a significant relationship between transformational leadership and commitment to change of teachers in Davao City?; (6) Is there a significant relationship between commitment to change and the organizational behavior of teachers in Davao City?; (7) Is there a significant mediating effect of commitment to change on the relationship between transformational leadership and the organizational behavior of teachers in Davao City?

This study is anchored on the Transformational Leadership Theory of Bass (1990). People who have transformational leadership possess four attributes to varying degrees (Bass, Avolio, & Atwater, 1996). They are idealized influence (highly liked role models), inspirational motivation (optimistic about goal attainment), intellectually stimulating (encourages critical thinking and problem-solving), and individualized consideration (shows empathy and purpose). Transformational leadership is a style of leadership where the achievement of group goals is contingent upon the support of the team. Boosting a group's spirits and self-assurance allows them to better connect with a larger goal or vision. This theory is aligned with the study since by serving as role models for desired behaviors and embodying the changes they seek to implement these leaders foster a culture of commitment to change within the organization. Additionally, by leveraging the principles of transformational leadership, organizations can enhance commitment to change, thereby increasing the likelihood of successful implementation and sustained adoption of transformative initiatives.

Materials and Methods

The researchers employ a quantitative, nonexperimental, correlational research design to examine the study's outcomes. Quantitative research utilizes statistical methodologies to analyze relationships among variables through surveys and experiments, generating empirical and objective data (Creswell & Creswell, 2022). This approach involves evaluating phenomena without directly manipulating variables within the study's context, with the correlational design used to scrutinize relationships between variables (Frey, 2018).

These methods form the foundation for addressing the research hypotheses. By employing these methodologies, the researchers aim to quantify insights into teachers' levels of commitment to change, transformational leadership, and organizational behavior in Davao City. Additionally, the study seeks to provide statistical evidence regarding the relationships between transformational leadership and commitment to change, commitment to change and organizational behavior, and transformational leadership and organizational behavior among teachers in Davao City. Furthermore, the research aims to explore the mediating effect of commitment to change on the relationship between transformational

leadership and teachers' organizational behavior. Through meticulous collection and statistical analysis of data, the researchers aim to gain an overall analysis of the study's variables and its respondents.

The researchers selected 183 teachers in Davao City through proportional quota sampling and adhered to the study's inclusion and exclusion criteria. Proportional quota sampling was chosen as the sampling technique of the study because it was used when the total number of people to be surveyed was typically decided in advance and the sample was split into subgroups (Sedgwick, 2012). The researchers obtained the respondents from every public or private tertiary-level institution in Davao City. To be admitted as one of the respondents of this study, the respondents were required to possess the following: Male or Female, 23-65 years old, and coming from recognized public and private educational institutions that offer tertiary levels in Davao City. The respondents were not admitted to the study on the following grounds: the respondent's age was not included in the age bracket provided above and were not teachers of any recognized public or private educational institutions in the locale.

The researchers adopted the following scales: Fedor and Colleague's Commitment to Change Scale, Avolio and Bass' Transformational Leadership Scale, and Bateman and Crant's Organizational Behavior Scale. Fedor and Colleague's Commitment to Change Scale aimed to assess the competency beliefs of school administrators. The scale was composed of 14 items further divided into 3 domains: affective with 6 items; continuance with 5 items; and normative with 3. Avolio and Bass' Transformational Leadership Scale sought to assess employees' transformational leadership levels in 4 domains. The scale was composed of 20 items which were further divided into 4 domains namely: idealized influence with 8 items; inspirational motivation with 4 items; intellectual stimulation with 4 items; and individual consideration with 4 items. Bateman and Crant's Organizational Behavior Scale sought to assess employees' organizational behavior which was a relatively stable tendency to effect environmental change. The scale was composed of 17 items measuring the organizational behavior of an employee.

In assessing the levels of commitment to change, transformational leadership, and organizational behavior among the respondents, the researchers employed various statistical analysis tools. Initially, the mean was utilized to gauge the levels of these variables within the dataset. Furthermore, to explore if there was a significant relationship between the variables in the study, the researchers applied the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (Pearson-r). Moreover, to identify if there was a mediating effect of commitment to change on the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational behavior, the researchers utilized Path Analysis. To facilitate these analyses, the researchers utilized the IBM-SPSS Statistics 26 software, a widely utilized platform in quantitative research. Subsequently, the treated data underwent comprehensive analysis and interpretation by the researchers, enabling a nuanced understanding of the dynamics between transformational leadership and organizational behavior.

The researchers abided by the guidelines established by the Research Ethics Committee of their affiliated institution. These guidelines encompass various assessment criteria, including but not limited to social value, informed consent, risk, benefits, and safety, privacy and confidentiality, justice, transparency, qualification of researchers, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement. Furthermore, these protocols are by the standards outlined by the Department of Science and Technology – Philippine Health Research and Ethics Board (DOST-PHREB) under the Republic Act No. 10532, also known as the Philippine National Health Research System (PNHRS) Act of 2013. The researchers are committed to ensuring that all participants in the study are treated with the utmost respect and provided with the necessary protection, recognizing these elements as pivotal to the study's success.

Before initiating data collection for this study, the researchers adhered to a structured sequence of steps. Firstly, they submitted a concept paper outlining the study's objectives to the professor responsible for overseeing the course on Theories and Models of Organization, seeking approval. Upon obtaining approval, the researchers proceeded to adopt the three established research instruments into their study: Fedor and Colleague's Commitment to Change Scale, Avolio and Bass' Transformational Leadership Scale, and Bateman and Crant's Organizational Behavior Scale. Subsequently, the researchers crafted an online form using Google Forms, integrating essential documents such as an informed consent form and a data privacy notice. These documents were presented to respondents before administering the research

instruments to ensure ethical considerations were met. Lastly, the researchers engaged with various private and public educational institutions at the tertiary levels in Davao City. This engagement occurred through personalized communication letters, aiming to introduce the research study and extend invitations to potential respondents, thereby facilitating their involvement in the study.

Results

This section presents the study's results after the data gathering and analysis. A discussion was added to supplement the data gathered and explained further by various literature supporting the study's results.

Table 1. Summary of the Level of Commitment to Change of Teachers in Davao City

Domains	Mean	Descriptive Level
Affective	3.50	Very High
Continuance	3.33	High
Normative	3.32	High
Overall	3.38	High

Table 1 shows the summary of the level of commitment to change among teachers in Davao City. The following indicators under commitment to change are affective, continuance, and normative. Among the indicators under commitment to change, affective got the highest mean of 3.50, or very high. Furthermore, the overall commitment to change got a mean score of 3.38, or high which indicates that commitment to change is evident among teachers in Davao City.

Table 2. Summary of the Level of Transformational Leadership of Teachers in Davao City

Domains	Mean	Descriptive Level
Idealized Influence	3.49	High
Inspirational Motivation	3.39	High
Intellectual Stimulation	3.45	High
Individual Consideration	3.34	High
Overall	3.42	High

Table 2 shows the summary of the level of transformational leadership among teachers in Davao City. The following indicators under idealized influence, inspiring motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual growth are characteristics of transformational leadership. Among the indicators under transformational leadership, idealized influence got the highest mean of 3.49, or high. Furthermore, overall transformational leadership got a mean score of 3.42 or high which indicates that transformational leadership is evident among teachers in Davao City.

Table 3. Summary of the Level of Organizational Behavior of Teachers in Davao City

Domains	Mean	Descriptive Level
Overall	3.46	High

Table 3 shows the summary of the level of organizational leadership among teachers in Davao City. This particular variable is a unidimensional variable which means that under this variable, there are no domains to be measured. The overall organizational behavior got a mean score of 3.46, or high which indicates that organizational behavior is evident among teachers in Davao City.

Table 4. Significant Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Commitment to Change of Teachers in Davao City

	Commitment to Change of Teachers in Davao City			
	r	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Transformational Leadership of Teachers in Davao City	.248	.001	Reject	There is a significant weak positive correlation

Table 4 shows the significance of the relationship between transformational leadership and commitment to change of teachers in Davao City. The overall p-value is .001, which is less than the .05 level of significance. This result shows a significant relationship between transformational leadership and commitment to change in teachers in Davao City. Also, the overall correlation coefficient of .248 shows a significant weak positive correlation between the two variables of the study. Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected.

Table 5. Significant Relationship between Commitment to Change and Organizational Behavior of Teachers in Davao City

	Organizational Behavior of Teachers in Davao City			
	r	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Commitment to Change of Teachers in Davao City	.261	.000	Reject	There is a significant weak positive correlation

Table 5 shows the significance of the relationship between commitment to change and the organizational behavior of teachers in Davao City. The overall p-value is .000, which is less than the .05 level of significance. This result shows a significant relationship between commitment to change and the organizational behavior of teachers in Davao City. Also, the overall correlation coefficient of .261 shows a significant weak positive correlation between the two variables of the study. Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected.

Table 6. Significant Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Organizational Behavior of Teachers in Davao City

	Organizational Behavior of Teachers in Davao City			
	r	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Transformational Leadership of Teachers in Davao City	.214	.004	Reject	There is a significant weak positive correlation

Table 6 shows the significance of the relationship between commitment to change and the organizational behavior of teachers in Davao City. The overall p-value is .004, which is less than the .05 level of significance. This result shows a significant relationship between transformational leadership and the organizational behavior of teachers in Davao City. Also, the overall correlation coefficient of .214 shows a significant weak positive correlation between the two variables of the study. Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected.

Table 7. Mediating Effect of Commitment to Change on the Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Organizational Behavior of Teachers in Davao City

Mediation Analysis Results	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p-value	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
Direct Effects						
Transformational Leadership → Organizational Behavior	0.161	0.073	2.198	0.028	0.017	0.304
Indirect Effects						
Transformational Leadership → Commitment to Change → Organizational Behavior	0.055	0.024	2.286	0.022	0.008	0.102
Total Effects						
Transformational Leadership → Organizational Behavior	0.216	0.073	2.972	0.003	0.073	0.358

Direct effects analysis reveals a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and organizational behavior (Estimate = .161, SE = .073, z = 2.198, p = .028). Indirect effects analysis demonstrates a significant indirect effect of transformational leadership on organizational behavior through a commitment to change (Estimate = .055, SE = .024, z = 2.286, p = .022). Total effects analysis further supports the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational behavior (Estimate = .216, SE = .073, z = 2.972, p = .003).

In examining the path coefficients, several key relationships emerge within the mediation model involving transformational leadership, commitment to change, and organizational behavior. The path coefficient between transformational leadership and organizational behavior (Estimate = .161, SE = .073, z = 2.198, p = .028) demonstrates a significant direct effect. Moreover, the path coefficient between transformational leadership and commitment to change (Estimate = .299, SE = .087, z = 3.449, p < .001) reveals a significant positive relationship. Furthermore, the path coefficient between commitment to change and organizational behavior (Estimate = .184, SE = .060, z = 3.054, p = .002) highlights a significant positive relationship, indicating that greater commitment to change is associated with improved organizational behavior. This path represents the mediating effect, as commitment to change serves as the mechanism through which transformational leadership influences organizational behavior.

Figure 1. Path Diagram of the Mediation Analysis Model in which Commitment to Change Mediates the Effect of Teachers’ Transformational Leadership on their Organizational Behavior

Legend: TrL: Transformational Leadership; CtC: Commitment to Change; OrB: Organizational Behavior

The type of mediation that occurred in this scenario is partial mediation. This is evident from the significant direct effect of transformational leadership on organizational behavior, even after accounting for the indirect effect mediated through commitment to change. Therefore, while commitment to change partially mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational behavior, there are additional pathways through which transformational leadership influences organizational behavior beyond its impact on commitment to change.

Discussion

Teachers in Davao City exhibit a high level of commitment to change. According to Purwanto, Purba, Bernarto, & Sijabat (2021), the analysis and testing results demonstrate that organizational citizenship behavior has a significant and beneficial effect on transformational leadership, positively and significantly impacts job satisfaction, and positively and significantly impacts organizational commitment. This study has demonstrated how organizational citizenship behavior in supply chain management deployed companies is influenced by transformational leadership, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction. Moreover, in the study of Liu (2016) he found that perceptions of instructors' commitment to change varied throughout age groups, and that perceptions are influenced differently by internal and external organizational factors.

Furthermore, the respondents exhibit a high level of transformational leadership. To create more capable leaders who can drive transformation in teacher training institutes, transformational leadership should be given priority. Moreover, transformational leadership alongside communication transparency must go along together. As explained by the study of Zainab, Akbar, & Siddiqui (2021), the acquisition of a sufficient and correct channel of communication becomes an avenue for employees to be open towards transformational change. Furthermore, they explained that through good transformational leadership, employees can speak out their suggestions which can better the organization as a result. Additionally, according to Yacon & Cayaban (2023) based on their evaluation, the utilization of transformational leadership among educators in its four dimensions has a positive impact on their organization although some problems are not directly related to the leadership styles since most of them are triggered by external factors.

Moreover, the respondents exhibit a high level of organizational behavior. To better understand, Sharma & Kaur (2024) highlighted that organizational behavior is a voluntary behavior exhibited by employees without expectation of something in return even if the job goes beyond their responsibilities. Since the respondents of this study exhibit high organizational behavior, it is manifested that the organization benefits from it. Moreover, this is supported by the study conducted by Nunez, Marquez, Zayas & Lopez (2020), employees who experience positive work behavior are more likely to improve internal situations because they manifest positive behavior such as taking responsibility intently, getting away from problems, and are more innovative. As a result, Ali & Wagar (2014) discussed based on the findings of their study that there is a direct relationship between schoolteachers' organizational behavior and the leadership style of the school heads. In other words, organizational behavior is greatly associated with leadership style. Teachers with the least organizational leadership are those subjected to a laissez-faire leadership style (Ali, et.al, 2014). Furthermore, Roncesvalles & Gaerlan (2021) elaborated that there is a strong influence of good and authentic leadership on the teacher's organizational behavior. Thus, the relationship between organizational leaders and employees must be given so much importance.

According to Hussain et al. (2016), a teacher's commitment to change is affected by the influence of the four separate parts of transformational leadership when applied in the instructional program. Additionally, using a specific leadership style aided by a strong authority may inspire commitment to change among employees. One of the leadership philosophies that a leader can apply to strengthen bonds with their team members is transformational leadership. The investigation results show compelling proof of a relationship between the variables. Change is highly valued by the team members of a leader who successfully applies a transformational leadership style (Astari & Martina, 2020). Moreover, employee

dedication to change, a byproduct of transformational leadership, is acknowledged as an internal innovation generator, in contrast to traditional tactics that encourage creativity through external rewards. Organizations often conserve resources during times of transition to be prepared for unanticipated occurrences that may affect their operations (To & Huang, 2022).

Additionally, Jun & Lee (2023), research emphasizes the critical function that leadership plays in fostering creative activity among staff members by influencing employees' perspectives. This research sheds new light on the role of leadership in the process by which leaders encourage innovative behavior among their workforce, given that businesses are compelled to increase their flexibility, responsiveness, and efficiency because of the dynamic and competitive environment, which leads to continuous innovation. With an emphasis on the moderating role of organizational support for creativity and the mediating role of employees' commitment to change, we believe this is one of the first attempts to present empirical evidence demonstrating the mechanism via which transformational leaders support their employees' innovative behavior. While many scholars have examined few research have examined how the attitudes of change recipients would moderate the link between leadership and results that are change-oriented. have examined the mediating role of employee commitment to change in the relationship between transformational leadership and employee innovative behavior (Oreg et al., 2011).

Conclusion

The study investigated the relationships among transformational leadership, commitment to change, and organizational behavior among teachers in Davao City. The results suggested that transformational leadership, commitment to change, and organizational behavior are evident among teachers in Davao City. The findings reveal significant positive relationships between these variables. Transformational leadership exhibited by teachers was found to have a significant direct effect on organizational behavior. Additionally, transformational leadership had a significant positive relationship with commitment to change among teachers. Commitment to change, in turn, was positively associated with organizational behavior, indicating that greater commitment to change leads to improved organizational behavior. The analysis further revealed that commitment to change partially mediated the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational behavior. It suggests that while transformational leadership directly influences organizational behavior, it also indirectly impacts organizational behavior through its effect on enhancing teachers' commitment to change.

The results highlight the importance of transformational leadership in fostering positive organizational behavior among teachers. By exhibiting idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration, transformational leaders can cultivate a stronger commitment to change within their followers. This commitment to change then contributes to more desirable organizational behaviors. Overall, the study underscores the crucial role of transformational leadership in facilitating organizational change and positive behavior within educational institutions. By promoting a transformational leadership style and nurturing a commitment to change among teachers, schools can create an environment conducive to organizational effectiveness and continuous improvement.

Recommendations

To fully comprehend the relationships between teachers' organizational behavior, transformational leadership, and commitment to change, future researchers should take into account the environment of school heads as a critical topic deserving of more study. In particular, investigating school heads' leadership philosophies, methods, and obstacles while advocating for a change-oriented culture in educational establishments may yield insightful information. Qualitative research centered on school heads' opinions and experiences navigating organizational change processes, as well as their relationships with faculty, may provide a wealth of data for analysis. Furthermore, the influence of school heads'

particular leadership behaviors and methods on teachers' organizational behavior and commitment to change should be investigated through quantitative study. Future research can help develop customized treatments and methods to improve leadership effectiveness and promote positive organizational behaviors inside schools by focusing on the role of school heads.

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